

DO I-PASS FOR FAIR?

Self assessment tool to measure the FAIR-ness of an organization

BEGINNER

INTERMEDIATE

ADVANCED

DOES YOUR ORGANIZATION...

- 1 POLICY**
...have a FAIR research data policy?
- 2 SERVICES**
...have a DCC which provides services to allow research(ers) to comply with FAIR?
- 3 SKILLS**
...acknowledge that FAIR capacity building requires specific roles and skills?
- 4 INCENTIVES**
...have incentives for FAIR data?
- 5 ADOPTION**
...have adoption of FAIR?

Find the checklist here
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Landelijk Coördinatiepunt
Research Data Management
The data support collective

My organization is FAIR enabling at level

Are the FAIR principles explicitly mentioned in the data (or research data) policy of your organization?

Which services does your organization provide (or refer to) in order for researchers to comply with the F principles

We provide a service to deliver a PID for a data set

We provide a service for PID and adding metadata (including reference to the dataset)

On top of adding PIDs and metadata, we provide or refer to a service to make the data findable through indexed resources

How much of your organizations scientific publications contain a PID reference to the data (take 2019)

<20% of the publications contain references to the underlying data.

20-80% of the publications contain references to the underlying data.

>80% of the publications contain references to the underlying data.

we do not know

What are your organization's most important challenges in becoming FAIR enabling?

